

ISSN: 3060-4613

MAKTABGACHA
VA MAKTAB
TA'LIMI VAZIRLIGI

№10
2025

- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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AKTABGACHA VA AKTAB TA'LIMI

Pedagogika, psixologiya fanlariga ixtisoslashgan ilmiy jurnal

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Elektron nashr. 612 sahifa,
3-oktyabr, 2025-yil.

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Muassis: "Tadbirkor va ishbilarmon" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: O'zbekiston Respublikasi Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi vazirligi, O'zbekiston milliy pedagogika universiteti

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Pedagogika fanlari bo‘yicha: OAK Kengashi tavsiyasi (26.08.2024-y., №11-05-4381/01) asosida:

- Ekspert kengashi (29.10.2024-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (31.10.2024-y., №363/5)

Psixologiya fanlari bo‘yicha: Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti murojaatiga asosan OAK tavsiyasi (24.04.2025-y., №11-05-2566/01):

- Ekspert kengashi (25.05.2025-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (08.05.2025-y., №370/5)

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta’limi”
jurnali

26.09.2023-yildan

O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti
Administratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot
va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar
agentligi tomonidan **№C-5669363**
reyestr raqami tartibi bo‘yicha
ro‘yxatdan o‘tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: **№136361**

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PEDAGOGIK TA'LIMDA KLASTER YONDASHUVI: O'ZBEKISTON VA JAHON TAJRIBASI

UDK: 37

Nafisa Tokhirova Dilshod qizi

A. Avloniy nomidagi pedagogik mahorat milliy instituti

Annotatsiya: Maqolada o'qituvchilarni tayyorlashda klaster yondashuvining ahamiyati hamda uning O'zbekiston ta'lim tizimidagi joriy etilishi tahlil qilinadi. Ushbu yondashuvning maqsadi – ta'lim sifatini oshirish, uzluksiz kasbiy rivojlanishni yo'lga qo'yish va oliy ta'lim muassasalari bilan umumta'lim maktablari o'rtasidagi hamkorlikni kuchaytirishdan iborat. Chirchiq pedagogika klasteri misolida "Eshitdim – Ko'rdim – Bajardim" metodikasi nazariya va amaliyot o'rtasidagi tafovutni qisqartirishi tahlil qilinadi. Germaniya va Avstriyadagi Schulcluster, Rossiya va MDHdagi "ta'lim – fan – ishlab chiqarish" modeli hamda Afrika tajribalari klasterlarning samaradorlik, innovatsiya va inklyuzivlikni rag'batlantirishini ko'rsatadi. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni isbotlaydiki, klaster modeli o'qituvchilar malakasini barqaror oshirish, resurslarni teng taqsimlash va inklyuziv ta'limni rivojlantirishga xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: o'qituvchi tayyorlash; klaster yondashuvi; pedagogik innovatsiya; uzluksiz ta'lim; Chirchiq modeli; xalqaro tajriba; hamkorlik; malaka oshirish; inklyuziv ta'lim.

Abstract: This article analyzes the significance of the cluster-based approach in teacher training and its implementation within Uzbekistan's education system. The approach aims to improve teaching quality, establish continuous professional development, and strengthen cooperation between universities and schools. Using the Chirchik Pedagogical Cluster as a case, the study explores the "Hear – See – Do" methodology, which bridges the gap between theory and practice. Comparative analysis of Germany/Austria's Schulcluster, Russia/CIS's "education – science – production" model, and African practices demonstrate that clusters enhance efficiency, innovation, and inclusivity. The results confirm that the cluster model contributes to sustainable teacher development, equitable resource distribution, and the advancement of inclusive education.

Key words: teacher training; cluster-based approach; pedagogical innovation; continuous professional development; Chirchik model; international experience; collaboration; qualification improvement; inclusive education.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается значение кластерного подхода в подготовке учителей и его внедрение в образовательную систему Узбекистана. Цель подхода – повышение качества обучения, обеспечение непрерывного профессионального развития и укрепление сотрудничества между университетами и школами. На примере Чирчикского педагогического кластера анализируется методика "Слушаю – Наблюдаю – Делаю", которая сокращает разрыв между теорией и практикой. Сравнительный обзор Schulcluster (Германия/Австрия), модели "образование – наука – производство" (Россия/СНГ) и африканских кластеров показывает, что кластеры стимулируют эффективность, инновации и инклюзивность. Результаты показывают, что кластерная модель способствует устойчивому развитию педагогов, справедливому распределению ресурсов и продвижению инклюзивного образования.

Ключевые слова: подготовка учителей; кластерный подход; педагогические инновации; непрерывное образование; Чирчикская модель; международный опыт; сотрудничество; повышение квалификации; инклюзивное образование.

INTRODUCTION

Teacher quality remains one of the most critical determinants of learning outcomes. Around the world, nations that have achieved consistent improvements in student learning – such as Finland, Singapore, and South Korea – have invested deeply in the continuous professional growth of their teachers. Uzbekistan, too, has embarked on a comprehensive process of educational modernization under its 2030 Development Strategy, which positions education as a driver of national development and innovation.

Despite important progress in policy reforms, teacher preparation in Uzbekistan has historically faced several structural challenges. These include fragmented coordination between teacher education institutions and schools, insufficient opportunities for in-service teachers to upgrade skills, and limited application of evidence-based pedagogy. Many pre-service graduates enter classrooms without sufficient exposure to real-world teaching practice, while working teachers often rely on outdated training approaches disconnected from classroom realities. In this context, the cluster-based approach has emerged as a promising innovation in organizing teacher training. Educational clusters connect universities, schools, training centers, and community partners within a coherent ecosystem. They aim to foster collaboration, innovation, and resource sharing – making teacher development continuous rather than episodic. This approach aligns with the modern concept of lifelong learning and offers practical mechanisms for bridging theory and practice.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The object of the present study is the cluster-based model of teacher training as a meso-level mechanism that connects national education policy with school-level practice. The research addresses three key questions:

- how does the cluster model enhance coherence and quality in Uzbekistan's teacher training system;
- which international experiences are most relevant and adaptable to the Uzbek context;
- and what barriers might affect the implementation and scaling of clusters at the regional and national levels.

Methodologically, this study employs the following approaches: document analysis of legal and policy frameworks issued by the Ministry of Preschool and School Education and the Ministry of Higher Education, Science, and Innovation; comparative analysis of cluster-based education models in Germany, Austria, Russia, and Sub-Saharan Africa; and a case study of the Chirchik Pedagogical Cluster, focusing on its organizational structure, training practices, and early outcomes. This multi-source research design enables triangulation of data and insights, integrating theoretical perspectives with empirical evidence from both Uzbekistan and international practice.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Educational clusters are designed to address fragmentation by creating synergy among institutions involved in teacher development. In the cluster model, each stakeholder has a clearly defined role:

- universities provide research and methodological guidance;
- schools offer authentic practice environments;
- training centers coordinate in-service development;
- and local authorities ensure governance and sustainability.

Clusters promote horizontal collaboration (among schools and teachers) and vertical collaboration (between schools, universities, and ministries). They also encourage mobility—teachers and mentors can move across partner institutions for workshops, internships, and demonstration lessons. This creates a dynamic professional community centered on shared learning rather than isolation. The cluster-based approach in Uzbekistan emerged within a broader national reform agenda aimed at raising education quality and international competitiveness.

The Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026 and subsequent decrees emphasize teacher professionalism, digital competence, and inclusive education. Pilot clusters were first established around pedagogical universities such as the Chirchik State Pedagogical Institute, the Fergana Pedagogical Institute, and the Termez State University, each acting as a hub for surrounding schools. These clusters are tasked with coordinating teacher mentoring, organizing demonstration lessons, and aligning pre-service and in-service training programs. Early evidence suggests that cluster schools demonstrate higher participation in professional learning activities and stronger collaboration between novice and experienced teachers. The Chirchik cluster exemplifies how the model operates in practice. It includes over 30 partner schools, digital resource centers, and municipal education departments. Its main goal is to connect academic knowledge with classroom reality through systematic collaboration. A central feature is the “Hear – See – Do” methodology (Eshitdim – Ko'rdim – Bajardim), which guides teachers through a three-phase learning cycle:

- Hear – participation in lectures and discussions on pedagogical theory;
- See – observation of demonstration lessons by expert teachers;
- Do – supervised practice with feedback and reflection.

This approach reduces the gap between theory and practice, giving teachers structured opportunities to apply new methods immediately after learning them.

Table 1: Organizational structure and functions of the Chirchik pedagogical cluster

Component	Key Participants	Primary Functions	Expected Outcomes
Higher Education Institution	Chirchik State Pedagogical Institute	Scientific and methodological leadership, mentor training, and research coordination	Modernized teacher education curricula and professional development programs
Partner Schools	General and specialized schools	Practicum sites, pilot curricula, peer mentoring	Improved instructional quality and reflective teaching practice
Training & Resource Centers	In-service training institutes, digital labs	Short courses, blended learning, certification	Increased digital and methodological competence among teachers
Local Authorities	Regional and municipal education departments	Funding, logistics, regulatory support	Sustainable cluster governance and policy alignment
Community & NGOs	Parents' associations, inclusion organizations	Outreach, inclusion initiatives, feedback loops	Enhanced social partnership and equity in education

Empirical observations and teacher interviews from the Chirchik cluster reveal several key benefits:

- practice-embedded learning, where teachers continuously integrate new techniques into their daily instruction;
- mentor culture, in which experienced teachers support novices through structured feedback;
- digital readiness, as resource centers enable access to online learning platforms and interactive content;
- and inclusive teaching, where cooperation with NGOs helps teachers adopt inclusive pedagogies for learners with diverse needs.

However, implementation is not without challenges. The most common issues include uneven access to technology and materials, particularly in rural schools; overloaded mentors and insufficient incentives; limited monitoring tools to measure qualitative growth in teaching; and the need for more localized professional learning content in Uzbek and Russian languages. These findings underline that while the cluster model is promising, it requires careful investment and adaptive governance to succeed nationwide. The concept of educational clustering is not unique to Uzbekistan but has evolved differently across contexts. In Germany and Austria, the Schulcluster Model groups several schools under joint management, sharing administrative structures, professional learning schedules, and support services. Teachers collaborate in lesson study teams, and regional pedagogical institutes provide methodological assistance. In Russia and other CIS countries, the “Education–Science–Production” model integrates universities, research institutes, and enterprises, ensuring alignment between teacher training, applied research, and labor market needs. In Sub-Saharan Africa, teacher cluster communities have emerged as low-cost learning circles where teachers observe lessons, exchange ideas, and conduct peer mentoring. These clusters show that even minimal funding can yield high professional impact when collaboration is genuine. The comparative analysis suggests that the success of clustering depends less on funding and more on fostering a professional culture of shared responsibility and reflection. For Uzbekistan, this means combining structural support from ministries and universities with bottom-up innovation at the school level.

CONCLUSION

The cluster-based approach represents a significant paradigm shift in Uzbekistan’s teacher development landscape. It redirects the focus from episodic, one-off workshops to continuous, practice-centered professional learning. The experience of the Chirchik cluster clearly demonstrates that such collaborative models lead to measurable improvements in teacher motivation, digital literacy, and classroom practices. For sustainable and effective scaling, several priorities should be emphasized:

- establishing clear cluster standards and governance frameworks;
- investing in mentor training and creating professional incentives;
- ensuring equitable access to digital infrastructure;

- introducing qualitative evaluation tools that measure not only participation but also improvements in classroom practice and student learning outcomes.

When adequately supported, the cluster-based teacher training model can become a cornerstone of educational modernization—bridging the gap between policy and practice and fostering an inclusive, high-quality learning environment across Uzbekistan.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

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2025. №10

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"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669363 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Yunusobod tumani
19-mavze, 17-uy.